

The Effects Of Environmental Conditions On The Strength Of Double Lap Joints

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Background

- Adhesive joints - lower weight, enhanced fatigue life and a more uniform stress distribution –
- Used for a variety of aircraft applications

Spoilers and Ailerons: Structural film adhesive core filler

Vertical tail plane: Structural film adhesive

Radome: Structural film adhesive

Horizontal tail plane: Structural fil/ Liquid adhesive

Landing Gear Door: Structural film adhesive

Wing: Acrylic paste adhesive for aluminium part identification

Background and Aims

- The **mechanical properties** of both the **adhesive and composite** adherend can be **severely affected** by **temperature and moisture**
- The **literature data** on the effects of temperature and humidity on adhesively bonded joints with composite **is limited** and **not well understood**
- Understand the effects of **increasing overlap length** on the **failure of double lap joints**
- Different environmental conditions considered: **Room Temperature Dry (RTD)**, **Hot Temperature Dry (HTD)** and **Hot Temperature Wet (HTW)**

Specimen Configuration

- **Adherends:** Hexcel HexPly[®] IM7/8552 carbon/epoxy pre-pregs with a stacking sequence of $[0/45/90/-45]_{ns}$
- **Adhesive:** Hexcel Redux[®] 319 film adhesive
- **Secondary Bonding**
- **Surface Preparation:** Grit-blasting ($1.8 \mu\text{m}$) and Liquid Degreasing
- Two overlap lengths of **12 mm** and **36 mm** tested

Experimental Results

- Material characterisation tests conducted to understand effects of temperature and moisture on material properties
- **12 mm overlap length:**
 - Significant decrease in failure load - failure controlled by the shear strength
- **36 mm overlap length:**
 - Limit approached based on the energy required for fracture propagation
 - No significant difference in strength - G_{IC} increases and G_{IIC} decreases

Failure Mechanism

12mm Overlap Length

- Patches of adhesive visible
- Failure controlled by adhesive strength properties
- Crack migration into 0° ply of inner adherend after propagation within adhesive

36mm Overlap Length

- Only 0° plies visible on both fracture surfaces
- Fracture dominated
- Crack initiated within the adhesive fillet
- Propagated into 0° ply of inner adherend

Thank You

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